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Data management plan (DMP)

brand-registration

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published data sets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf

1 Data description

1a Lists of data sets that will be reused or produced

Produced data sets

dataset ID	name	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	brand-registrations-[DDMMYYYY].csv	Output table	csv	100 MB	no
P2	Brand-registrations-bar-plot-[DDMMYYYY].png	Output plot	png	100 MB	no

Reused data sets

dataset ID	name	format	DOI and license / source	contains sensitive data
R1	brand-registration-2017.csv	csv	License: Datenlizenz Deutschland – Namensnennung – Version 2.0 Source: govData Germany	no
R2	brand-registration-2019.csv	csv	License: Datenlizenz Deutschland – Namensnennung – Version 2.0 Source: govData Germany	No
R3	Code repository	Github repository	DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6501797 License: MIT	no

The dataset R3 encompasses the implementation of the experiment. Instructions to run the experiment can be found in the file Readme.md. The datasets P1, P2, R1, R2 can also be found in the code repository.

1b Data generation and reuse

Data generation

The input data was generated by the German Patent and Trademark Office and was published on GOVDATA (German's data registry). In this experiment the input data is preprocessed and a comparison is made for the amount of brand registrations from 2017 and 2019. This is done with the programming language Python. The output contains a bar plot, showing the amounts, and a csv file, listing the number of registrations per company.

It is not planned that new data is being collected. If other data sources are being used for this experiment, the preprocessing steps have to be adjusted.

A reference to additional information to the input data can be found in the Readme.md and in the metadata.

Data reuse

The input and output data can be found in the directory data. All datasets can be used according the specified license.

The source code itself can be used and adapted for further experiments. For more information please read the license information declared in the code repository.

2 Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in the file Readme.md. Version control is automated.

Metadata information can be found under documentation/metadata.xml.

The following domain specific metadata standard is used: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse the data.

Additionally, common metadata such as title, description or keywords are provided in the open access repository.

Controlled vocabularies for the data is used to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2b Data quality control

Data quality checks will be done, e.g. checks of consistency of labels, logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control.

3 Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project coordinator. A public gitHub repository will be accessible. More information about the provided license can be found there.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

I pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to the data during research:

Modifying the project is only possible for project members. But it is still possible for the public to work with an individual version. For this the project can be forked from gitHub.

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only
R3	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4 Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of my data.

4c Ethical issues

As this experiment is not using any sensitive information and all used data is public available, ethical issues are not a concern. If, in the future, these circumstances are changing, ethical issues will be discussed with the Research Ethics Coordinator at TU Wien (<https://www.tuwien.at/en/research/rti-support/research-ethics/>).

The research has not been reviewed yet by any ethics committee.

5 Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	license
P1	Open	2022-04-30	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6501809	CC Attribution 4.0 International
P2	Open	2022-04-30	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6501816	CC Attribution 4.0 International

The repository used in this project described in the following paragraph.

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com>

Specific tool or software is required to access and reuse the data: Using this data a machine running python is required. All specific libraries used are listed in the file requirements.txt and running the experiment is explained in the file Readme.md.

5b Long-term preservation and reusability

dataset ID	location for long-term storage (min. 10 years)	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6501809	forever	People interested in economics, specifically economics statistics.
P2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6501816	forever	People interested in economics, specifically economics statistics.
R3	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6501797	forever	The target audience are students and the general public because this experiment is illustrating the use of a DMP in a small software project and the output data could be useful for people interested in economics.

6 RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Martin Szewieczek will direct the data management process overall, is responsible for ensuring metadata production, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.